

Studies on Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Nickel(II) with Dibasic Acids as Primary and Heterocyclic Amines as Secondary Ligands

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A number of metal complexes of the type $K[NiL_2a(H_2O)(OH)]$, where L= isoquinoline or pyridine and a=deprotonated malonic, succinic, glutaric or adipic acid have been prepared and characterised on the basis of chemical analysis, conductance and magnetic measurements, I.R. and electronic spectral studies. All the complexes were found to have an octahedral structure.

THE survey of the existing literature reveals that the complexes of Ni(II) acetate with heterocyclic ligands and the mixed complexes of Ni(II) with aliphatic monobasic acids as primary and isoquinoline as secondary ligand¹⁻⁷ have been studied in relation of their preparation, chemical analysis and magnetic measurements. Recently the preparation and characterisation of bis(ethyl malanato) Ni(II) with nitrogen donors have been carried out by Mohapatra et al⁸. In this present communication we deal with the preparation and characterisation, of the mixed complexes of Ni(II) using malonic, succinic, glutaric and adipic acids as primary and pyridine and isoquinoline as secondary ligands.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions: The organic acids, Nickel(II) chloride, potassium hydroxide, all were of A.R. quality. Isoquinoline and pyridine were fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. All the solvents were also purified by carrying out their distillation.

Physical Measurements: Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy method at room temperature.

Reflectance spectra were obtained with a Carl Zeiss SPEKOL spectrophotometer, fitted with a reflectance attachment of type Rd/O. Electrical conductances were measured with an Systronics conductivity bridge type 302. The infrared spectra were run on Beckman IR-20 Spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were run on a Carl Zeiss SPECORD UV-Vis recording spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Complexes: An ethanolic solution of hydrated nickel chloride (1 mole) was mixed with ethanolic solutions of the organic acid (1 mole) and potassium hydroxide (3 moles). The precipitated potassium chloride was filtered off and the solution was concentrated and then filtered directly into an ethanolic solution of heterocyclic amine (pyridine or isoquinoline) (2.5 moles). The resulting mixture was kept overnight in an ice bath. The blue or bluish green crystalline complexes were filtered, washed several times with ethanol and finally with carbon tetrachloride and then dried in air.

The analysis for the metal, carbon and hydrogen, values of magnetic moments and molar conductances are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCES OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF NICKEL(II)

Compound	Colour	Metal (%)		Carbon (%)		Hydrogen (%)		Molar Conductance	off B.M.
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
$K[Ni(IQ)_2M(H_2O)(OH)]$	light blue	10.81	10.89	51.58	51.10	3.81	3.85	98	2.84
$K[Ni(IQ)_2S(H_2O)(OH)]$	light blue	10.53	10.69	52.69	52.06	4.09	4.14	104	2.89
$K[Ni(IQ)_2G(H_2O)(OH)]$	light blue	10.24	10.39	53.51	52.90	4.58	4.40	128	2.87
$K[Ni(IQ)_2A(H_2O)(OH)]$	light blue	9.97	10.04	54.47	53.81	4.61	4.67	119	2.92
$K[Ni(Py)_2M(H_2O)(OH)]$	greenish blue	13.60	13.67	40.28	39.69	3.77	3.82	120	3.40
$K[Ni(Py)_2S(H_2O)(OH)]$	greenish blue	12.08	13.19	41.88	41.27	4.14	4.18	132	3.33
$K[Ni(Py)_2G(H_2O)(OH)]$	green (light)	12.43	12.52	43.27	42.75	4.47	4.51	125	3.21
$K[Ni(Py)_2A(H_2O)(OH)]$	light blue	12.29	12.35	44.48	44.13	4.77	4.82	125	3.37

M=Malonate ion, S=Succinate ion, G=Glutarate ion, A=Adipate ion, IQ=Isoquinoline and Py=Pyridine.

Results and Discussion

The values of molar conductances in methanol indicated the bioelectrolytic nature of the complexes. The values of magnetic moments fall in the range 2.83-3.4 BM which is the general characteristic of octahedral complexes of nickel(II). The electronic spectra gave the usual three main bands, characteristic of octahedral complexes, at 9174 cm^{-1} (ν_1), 14600 cm^{-1} (ν_2) and 24700 cm^{-1} (ν_3) which are assigned to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively.

The reflectance spectra of these complexes also gave these three bands which indicate that no dissociation of the complexes occur in methanolic solutions.

The values of $10 Dq$, B (Spin allowed transition) and β_{3g} (inner configuration transition) have been calculated by using the following equations

$$\nu_1 = 10 Dq$$

$$B = \frac{(\nu_2 + \nu_3 - \nu_1)}{15}$$

and
$$\beta_{3g} = \frac{B_{\text{complex}}}{B_{\text{free ion}}}$$

which were found to be 9174 cm^{-1} , 785 and 0.74 respectively.

The infrared spectra of all the complexes were alike in appearance indicating their isostructural nature. The bands due to C...C and C...N stretching of the heterocyclic amine were shifted from 1500 and 1590 cm^{-1} to 1515 and 1600 cm^{-1} respectively indicating their coordination through N atom⁹.

The stretching bands obtained at 1724 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} due to C=O and COO in spectrum of malonic acid were shifted to 1630 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} respectively in the spectra of its complexes. In the case of succinic acid complexes the strong band obtained at 1730 cm^{-1} was shifted to 1640 cm^{-1} . This band was obtained at 1695 cm^{-1} in the case of glutaric acid and was shifted to 1630 cm^{-1} in the case of its complexes. The band obtained at 1700 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of adipic acid was shifted to 1600 cm^{-1} in the spectra of its complexes. These observations indicate the coordination of acids through oxygen. The bands due to M-O and M-N bond were obtained at 500 cm^{-1} and 620 cm^{-1} respectively.

A broad band obtained at 3200 cm^{-1} and a sharp band at 1100 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of water and (OH) group inside of the coordination sphere.

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